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Title: From Fear to Fluency: A Basis for Crafting Support Mechanism in Reducing Public Speaking Anxiety

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Abstract

The importance of oral presentation skills is evident through its increasingly regular use in professional and academic settings, therefore, included as a core area of language learning. Speaking is one of the most challenging macro-linguistic skills to develop among learners, hence, public speaking is usually the most common activity that individuals dislike, fear, or avoid. Hence, this study aims to identify the level of public speaking anxiety among senior high school students in selected schools in Bayombong, Bambang and Dupax del Norte, Nueva Vizcaya. The study employed the quantitative approach with mixed methods, and purposive sampling in selecting the respondents. The results showed that a significant proportion of students experienced high levels of anxiety. Also, variables such as sex, type of school and strand are associated with differences in anxiety, while first language is not. Moreover, exposure to English reading materials has a limited relationship with public anxiety among students. Ultimately, the study also aims to serve as a basis in crafting a support mechanism that is geared towards the optimization of oral communication skills among students through the reduction of speech anxiety. The proposed support mechanism is titled, "Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism". Therefore, this study has pedagogical implications for teaching and learning public speaking.

Keywords: public speaking anxiety, oral communication skills, anxiety reduction, support mechanism

Introduction

Language is conceived as a cultural characteristic which allows speech and speech communities to express their identities, backgrounds, and group membership. Since people value certain things and perform activities in a particular way, they come to employ language in ways which are reflective of what they value and what they do. Anchored on the humanist and functionalist perspective, Blommaert and Jie (2010) assert that "Language is approached as something that has a certain relevance to man, and man in anthropology is seen as a creature whose existence is narrowly linked, conditioned or determined by society,

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community, the group, culture” (p. 4). Through time, human beings have developed communication systems that allow them to use language in broad domains of encounter ranging from narrowly defined bilateral relationships to complex international relations. The language of international communication is English. If individuals are to enter a global workforce, there is a need for them to have a good command of English, both in oral and written forms. To remain competitive, Filipino students should not only have strong educational background but should also be armed with good communication skills.

As the lingua franca, English has the power of connecting people from many different cultures, building relationships, and fostering understanding. English has practically become a major language in recent years. Given its functional and communicative significance, English is one of the main subjects included in the curriculum, hence, it is being taught in primary, junior, senior high school and tertiary levels. Despite having language classes for several years, students view English as a challenging subject matter, especially developing proficiency in oral communication skills. Given this scenario, the provision of innovative learning strategies for oral communicative competence is integral in the language classroom.

Public Speaking Performance and Public Speaking Anxiety

Though English is one of the dominant languages used in the academic institutions the Philippines, there are still several factors that trigger speech anxiety among students. Grice and Skinner (2008) posit that public speaking is one of the most common social phobias. As defined by McCroskey (1977), “it is a predisposition to veer away from communication, if possible, or suffer a variety of fear or anxiety linked with real or anticipated communication with another individual or group” (p. 192). Native speakers as well as Filipinos suffer from communication apprehension. Public speaking anxiety poses a negative impact to a student. This may affect a learner’s capacity to succeed in a classroom (Bodie, 2010). Even experienced speakers have some anxiety when speaking in front of a group of people. Many people, especially those who have low self-confidence, feel anxious in almost any situation in which they might be evaluated. A student who believes that one must never say anything in English until it can be said correctly will probably avoid speaking most of the time. In 2020, Kang posits that fear often stems from a fear of negative evaluation and the potential for embarrassment can significantly hinder language learners’ willingness to engage in speaking activities.

Likewise, the study of Wulandari et al. (2022) reveals that students felt that psychological problems which include anxiety and low confidence have more impact on their speaking difficulties rather than linguistic problems. Altun (2023) described anxiety as the feeling of tension, nervousness, and fear while speaking in English. Due to excessive fear, emotions, and worry in various social settings or speeches like in oral presentations or public

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speeches where they speak in front of an audience, anxiety operates as an internal conflict that affects one's oral communication performance. People who suffer from public speaking anxiety have the tendency to avoid situations where they have to perform, however, when faced with such situations, these people suffer from intense anxiety and distress. During discussions and speaking activities, students tend to become quiet all the time, which may be more than just shyness. This is not only a difficulty that students contend with, but also something that a teacher needs to identify for appropriate instruction and remediation (Damayanti and Listyani, 2020). These problems can act as barriers in achieving personal and professional goals.

A student's motivation, self-confidence and anxiety are contributory factors in acquiring and utilizing a second language. The Affective Filter Hypothesis by Krashen (1982) posits that in every second language acquisition, several affective variables play a facilitative but non-causative role. Krashen (1982) claims that language acquisition becomes easier if a learner has a low level of anxiety, positive self-image, high motivation, and confidence. A learner's high affective filter, debilitating anxiety, low self-esteem, negative self-image, and low motivation may hamper the acquisition of a second language. Several studies confirm the impact of speech anxiety to the oral communication performance of students. Goh and Burns (2012), observed that anxiety adversely affects learners and leaves them stressed out. This type of experience creates hurdles for learners and compels them to step back from participating in speaking activities. Recent evidence by Tsang (2020), proves a clear relationship between tertiary students' self-perceived competence in delivering oral presentations and their levels of anxiety in public speaking. Moreover, Sulistyowati (2023) found that students feel uneasy, unconfident, nervous, and afraid of speaking English as a foreign language, thus, affecting their speaking motivation and fluency during class presentations and discussions. Hence, as evidenced by the literatures mentioned, there is an immense potential value in harnessing ESL learners' perceptions of their own presentation delivery skills as a means of lowering their anxiety.

Public Speaking Anxiety and Predictors

Hasibuan, et al. (2020) examined the impact of speaking anxiety and speaking performance among seventy-eight college freshmen in a university in Indonesia. Data were collected using the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (Richmond & McCroskey, 1998), questionnaire and speech scores. It was found that speaking anxiety was correlated to the students' speaking performance. Moreover, fear and nervousness affect oral language production. Likewise, Plandano, et al. (2023) sought to examine the level of public speaking anxiety among eighty-one college students at a university in Mindanao. Using quantitative

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descriptive survey design, it was found that the students experienced very high Audience Anxiety. However, the findings revealed no significant difference in the participants' level of anxiety when grouped according to profile, which means that anxiety level remains the same regardless of sex, age, and year level. As regards gender, same is true with the study of Alamri and Qasem (2024). Findings of the study indicated there is no significant difference between genders on the overall measure of speaking anxiety and the causes in foreign language setting of the study. Furthermore, the study indicated that undergraduate Saudi students with good proficiency level and students who were in higher academic level found to have less speaking anxiety. The prevailing causes of students' speaking anxiety found in the study were: fear of making mistakes, shyness, fear of teacher's negative techniques of error correction, fear of their classmates' laugh and remarks, lack of good preparation, and lack of speaking practice in the target language. However, Linter & Belovecova (2025) found that gender is a demographic predictor of public speaking anxiety in a large university in Czech Republic. The study found that women, non-binary individuals, graduates of academic high schools, and bachelor's students are more prone to public speaking anxiety. These findings highlight the need for targeted intervention and support strategies for students with higher levels of public speaking anxiety. The researchers posit that higher anxiety levels among females may be related to negative stereotypes accorded to females as people tend to give higher expectations regarding oral communication-related performances among women.

Gabaini and Elmenfi (2014) conducted a study which revealed factors that lead to the speaking anxiety of post-graduate students who attended intensive English language program in a Malaysian university. During classroom presentations, interviews, or speech deliveries, the respondents indicated that they experience communication apprehension, thus, making them preform ineffectively in various communication situations. The results implied that students who lack competence in English are more likely to feel anxious as opposed to those who possess good English language skills.

In the same pursuit, Haloc (2016) examined college sophomores' performance in impromptu speech and its relation to levels of speech anxiety. It was found that the respondents' level of oral performance in impromptu is generally satisfactory. This means that the college sophomores have acceptable performance in content, physical delivery, language use, technique and strategy and the use of attention-getter. However, the college sophomores' level of anxiety is very high. With that, possible interventions were recommended such as adapting current strategies in managing speech anxiety, creating a relaxed classroom atmosphere and balance between individual and collaborative speaking tasks. The intrinsic relationship between confidence and oral proficiency is further established in an earlier work of Querol, James, Haloc, Paulino and Gatan (2015). The study revealed that the proficiency and level of confidence among college freshmen required

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immediate and intensive focus. The provision of dynamic, creative, and critical approaches in teaching oral communication is deemed necessary as this pave the way for the holistic language development of the learners.

Public Speaking Anxiety among Senior High School Students

Among the few researchers on level of public speaking anxiety among senior high school students was conducted by Aricheta et al. (2024). The study employed James McCroskey's Personal Report on Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA) to determine the student's level of anxiety in public speaking. The results showed that the respondents had a moderately high level of anxiety. Also, variables such as strand, school graduated from, and socioeconomic status have no significant difference in their speech anxiety. Then, the sex of the respondents was found to have no significant difference with the respondents' speech anxiety. Furthermore, it was found that fear of negative evaluation is the most common reason why students experience speech anxiety. Meanwhile, preparation is the most effective way to use as a strategy in coping with speech anxiety.

Best Practices in Public Speaking Education

Despite the significant presence of speaking anxiety, a vast amount of research has focused on mechanisms designed to reduce learners' public speaking anxiety. A common method in public speaking anxiety is called cognitive modification. This is based on the assumption that anxiety in public speaking comes from negative thoughts about public speaking (Allen, Hunter, & Donohue, 1989). Cognitive modification procedures attempt to replace problematic public speaking cognitions with more positive views of public speaking and the self as a public speaker. These procedures include teaching students to personally identify negative feelings and encourage students to replace these irrational thoughts with positive attitudes. Moreover, the instructors may focus on strength-based feedback as this may eliminate negative perceptions of public speaking (Westwick, 2014). Furthermore, cognitive modification, and skills training can have a significant impact on anxiety reduction.

Creating an engaging and exciting learning atmosphere is important when requiring students to fulfill a speaking task. According to Walters, et al. (2022), self-esteem, self-confidence and improving collaborative skills can be harnessed through positive interaction with teachers and peers. One method of encouraging collaboration and engagement is incorporating games and related activities. The collaborative work required for this activity creates a sense of community as well which helps ease anxiety students may feel.

Student awareness of learning and setting of expectations are also necessary. Students must become aware of their own learning and decide what effective speaking looks

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like (Montag, 2023). Instructors may involve students in the creation of evaluative materials or to explore on presentation skills creatively. Involving students in the creation of the rubric forces them to think about presentation skills in a different way. Confidence in their speaking abilities will strengthen if students are more aware of how they will be assessed. As said by Montag (2023, p. 19), "By taking responsibility of their learning and understanding of speaking requirements, students are more likely to be able to meet the expectations their teachers have of them and feel more comfortable in their abilities."

In the survey of related literatures and studies, it was revealed that there is a dearth of research on the level of speech anxiety among Senior High School students in English as a Second Language (ESL) classrooms. In this light, this study is important in developing awareness among students as regards factors that influence their public speaking anxiety and public speaking performance. Ultimately, the study aims to serve as a basis in crafting a support mechanism that is geared towards the optimization of oral communication skills among students through the reduction of speech anxiety.

Theoretical Framework

The paper frames its analysis on Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982) and Canale and Swain's Communicative Competence Model (1980). The Affective Filter Hypothesis is one of the hypotheses on second language acquisition proposed by Krashen. This hypothesis discusses how affective factors establish causal connection to the second language acquisition process. Krashen claims that language acquisition is easier for a learner who has low affective filter. Language proficiency may be marked not only by competence in listening, reading, and writing. Speaking or oral language is of prime significance as oral language interactions are evident in our daily lives, thus, a learner's affective filter is contributory to his/her success or failure in oral speech exercises.

Krashen in 1982 suggested the concept of Affective Filter, and its congruence with the theoretical work done in the realm of second language acquisition and affective variables. Research had corroborated that success in second language acquisition relate to varied affective variables. Moreover, this hypothesis posits that people differ with respect to their affective filters. Learners whose attitudes are not satisfactory tend to get less input and strong affective filter. Those whose attitudes are optimal for second language acquisition will not only have weaker affective filter but also achieve more input.

In this study, the level of speech anxiety was measured through the Personal Report on Public Speaking Anxiety designed by Virginia P. Richmond and James C. McCroskey in 1998. Moreover, Canale and Swain's Communicative Competence Paradigm was included within the analytical frame. This paradigm entails both the learner's capacity to employ grammatical rules and his/her ability to appropriate spoken discourse in various

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communication contexts. A competent user of English should possess not only sociolinguistic and conversational skills but also linguistic knowledge. Canale and Swain's Paradigm encompasses grammatical competence, socio-linguistic competence, and strategic competence both in oral and written form.

Grammatical knowledge encompasses specific areas such as morphology, syntax, and phonology. These areas enable an individual to recognize and form acceptable grammatical structures and aid in comprehending content. Furthermore, sociolinguistic competence is the awareness of sociolinguistic conventions for constructing and using utterances which are acceptable in specific language situations. Lastly, strategic competence is viewed as an array of metacognitive factors which allow a communicator to be involved in planning, setting goals and appraising communicative sources. This knowledge allows a communicator to work effectively in small or big communication settings. The scoring rubric to be used in assessing the speaking performance is anchored on these communicative approaches.

Other variables include sex, strand, first language and exposure to English reading materials which may predict the respondents' level of speech anxiety.

Conceptual and Analytical Framework

This study is among the few to employ senior high school students as respondents in terms of public speaking anxiety and its possible predictors. As regards level of public speaking anxiety, a published tool will be used. This tool will measure the level of speech anxiety by the students prior, during and after a speech delivery. As has been discussed, there is a need to look into the possible relationship that exists between the two spontaneous speech activities and the level of public speaking anxiety as the latter may adversely impact the speech performance and eventually, the communicative growth of the learners.

The study will mechanize within the paradigm shown in Figure 1. It is assumed that there exists a possible relationship between the level of public speaking anxiety, sex, strand, first language and exposure to English reading materials. Thus, the researchers would like to create a baseline study that aims to provide reference for the crafting of a sustainable support mechanism that is geared towards the optimization of oral communication skills among Senior High School students through the recognition of factors affecting communication apprehension and the reduction of speech anxiety.

Figure 1
Research Paradigm

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Statement of the Problem

The study generally aims to examine the factors that affect the level of public speaking anxiety among Senior High School students. The study was conducted from August 2024 to April, 2025. Specifically, it aims to answer the following:

1. What is the level of public speaking anxiety of the students?
2. Is there a significant difference in the public speaking anxiety of the students when grouped according to
 2. 1. sex
 2. 2 strand
 2. 3 first language
 2. 4. exposure to English reading materials
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' level of public speaking anxiety and exposure to English reading materials?
4. What support mechanism can be crafted to help students reduce their public speaking anxiety?

Statement of Null Hypothesis

In view of the aforementioned problems, the following null hypotheses are forwarded:

1. There is no significant difference in the public speaking anxiety of the students when grouped according to
 3. 1. sex
 3. 2 strand

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- 3. 3 first language
 - 3. 4. exposure to English reading materials
2. There is no significant relationship between the students' level of public speaking anxiety and exposure to English reading materials.

Methodology

A. Design

This study employed the descriptive design using both quantitative and qualitative approaches to explore the senior high school level of speech anxiety as well as their possible predictors. Furthermore, it analyzed the possible difference between the profile variables: sex, strand, first language, exposure to English reading materials and level of public speaking anxiety. The relationship between level of public speaking anxiety and exposure to English reading materials was tested using the correlational method. Eventually, thematic analysis. Was used to examine the qualitative responses of the respondents. This allowed the researchers to look into insights regarding the management and eventual reduction of public speaking anxiety.

B. Locale

Figure 2
Research Environment

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This study was conducted in senior high schools in Nueva Vizcaya province, Region 02, Philippines. The study included 4 public and private senior high schools in Nueva Vizcaya, 1 senior high school from Bayombong, 2 senior high schools from Bambang, and 1 from Dupax del Norte. These were:

1. Saint Mary's University Senior High School
2. Bambang National High School
3. Saint Catherine's School
4. Lamo National High School

C. Research Participants and Sample

The respondents of the study were grade 11 students at the identified senior high schools of Nueva Vizcaya belonging to the following strands: Technical-Vocational-Livelihood Track (TVL), Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), Humanity and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Accountancy and Business Management (ABM). These strands include Oral Communication subject in their curriculum. Moreover, they were chosen as respondents because the researchers deem that harnessing their public speaking skills is necessary in preparing them for further academic rigors in tertiary education. In choosing the participants, clustered random sampling was employed. Each cluster is represented per identified senior high school. The following table shows the population of each participant school and sample size utilized in the study:

Table 1. *Population and Sample Size of Grade 11 Students of Saint Mary's University Senior High School, Bambang National High School, Saint Catherine's School and Lamo National High School for A.Y. 2024-2025*

Senior High School	Number of Students Enrolled	Sample Size
Saint Mary's University Senior High School	454	209
Bambang National High School	830	263
Saint Catherine's School	219	140
Lamo National High School	168	118
Total Number of Students Enrolled	1671	730

The sample size was determined via Sample Size Calculator by Raosoft, Inc. This software is believed to provide meaningful size results for an inquiry utilizing sampling techniques. As regards student interviewees, the researchers employed convenience sampling which involved the selection of participants who were willing to participate in the interview. Since this study sought parental consent, 440 respondents agreed to participate in the study. Table 2 shows the profile characteristics of the respondents.

Table 2. Profile Characteristics of Respondents

Profile	Groups	f (n=440)	Mean
Sex	Male	160	3.36
	Female	280	3.78
Type of School	Public	308	3.54
	Private	132	3.82
Strand	TVL	146	3.79 ^A
	STEM	120	3.64 ^A
	HUMSS	88	3.70 ^A
	ABM	86	3.22 ^B
First Language	Ilocano	119	3.71
	Filipino	278	3.56
	English	18	3.67
	Cordilleran language/s	25	3.84

As gleaned from Table 2, 404 senior high school students participated in the study. Out of these, 280 or 64% are female and 160 or 36% are males. Meanwhile, 308 or 70% of the respondents came from public schools and 132 or 30% study in public schools. As regards strand, most of the respondents belonged to the Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) strand, followed by Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, Humanity and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Accountancy and Business Management (ABM) strands, respectively. For first language as a profile variable, 278 or 63% consider

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Filipino as their first language, 119 or 27% respondents speak Ilocano as their first language, 25 or 6% for Cordilleran languages, and 18 or 4% for English.

D. Research Instruments

The researchers used a questionnaire which is composed of two parts. The first part included the demographic profile of the respondents. The second part of the questionnaire contained the Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety statements used to account for the level of speech anxiety. A published tool called Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety adapted from Richmond and McCroskey's (1998), "Communication Apprehension, Avoidance and Effectiveness". Hunter (2014 in Haloc, 2016) posits that the tool is known for its strong reliability and validity. Moreover, the Council for Aid to Education, deems this tool to be trustworthy as it fulfills the criteria for assessment measures. It has strong reliability and validity and is viewed as trustworthy in evaluating significant skills and has been proven relevant to students' learning experience (Benjamin, et al, 2009 in Hunter, 2014). Furthermore, the tool is composed of thirty-four statements about how one feels in communicating with other people. The respondents indicated the degree to which the statements apply to them by marking 1 for strongly agree; 2 for agree; 3 for undecided, 4 for disagree, or 5 for disagree. Moreover, a structured interview was conducted among randomly chosen respondents to gather responses as to possible strategies and interventions valuable to the crafting of a mechanism to effectively reduce anxiety related to public speaking performances.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

Once approval was granted, the research instrument was made and was validated by experts. The researchers sent letters to the participating schools to seek permission for the conduct of the study. The questionnaires were administered face-to-face with the help of their oral communication teachers. The interview was conducted in an area where noise and other interferences were kept at a minimum. All interview responses were treated with utmost confidentiality. Moreover, Informed Consent Forms were be given to students below 18, alongside Parental Consent. After collecting the questionnaire, the researcher collected and analyzed the data at hand for further interpretation.

F. Treatment of Data

To determine the PRPSA score, the following steps were applied:

- Step 1. Add the scores for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 10, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, and 34
- Step 2. Add the scores for items 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 24, and 26

Step 3. Complete the following formula: $PRPSA = 72 - \text{Total from Step 2} + \text{Total from Step 1}$.

The score should range between 34 and 170, otherwise, there is an error in the computation. To determine the level of speech anxiety of the respondents, their PRPSA scores were categorized according to the following scale shown in Table 1.

Table 2. *Richmond and McCroskey's Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (1998)*

PRPSA SCORE	Qualitative Description	Interpretation
between 34 and 84	Very low level of anxiety	Very few public speaking situations would produce anxiety
between 85 and 92	Moderately low level of anxiety	Some public speaking situations would be likely to arouse anxiety in people with such scores, most situations would not be anxiety arousing
between 93 and 110	Moderate anxiety	Moderate anxiety is felt but the level of anxiety is not likely to so severe that the individual would not be able to cope with it and eventually become a successful speaker
between 111 and 119	Moderately high level of anxiety	They tend to avoid public speaking because it usually arouses a fairly high level of anxiety, while some situations may not cause too much of a problem, most will be problematic.
between 120 and 170	Very high level of anxiety	They tend to have a range of very high anxiety in most, if not all, public speaking situations and are likely to go to considerable lengths to avoid them. It is unlikely they can become successful public speakers unless they overcome or significantly reduce their anxiety.

Thematic analysis and coding were employed to ascertain responses gathered via interview. Due to time constraints, interviews were done online. The responses sought to further explore factors that led to public speaking anxiety and forward possible recommendations on strategies for overcoming this. These may prove insightful to the teaching and learning of oral communication among senior high school students. In determining the significant difference between level of speech anxiety when respondents were grouped according to the profile variables, T-test and ANOVA were used, while significant correlation was determined through the computation of the Pearson-r statistical test.

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G. Ethical Considerations

Upon the approval of the evaluators, this study was submitted for approval to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) on 2nd floor, Rev. John Van Bauwel Hall, SMU Main Campus, Ponce Street, Don Mariano Marcos; Bayombong, 3700 Nueva Vizcaya, Philippines (email: reb@smu.edu.ph; cellphone: 09177053041). Also, the researchers sent consent letters to the officers-in-charge of the participating senior high schools to seek permission for the conduct of the study.

H. Conflict of Interest

There is no known conflict of interest in this study.

I. Confidentiality and Data Protection

The data in this study was treated with utmost confidentiality. The respondents were treated with anonymity. Only the researchers had access to the data, once the data have been collected. After the conduct of the study, the researchers will discard both hard and soft copies of the data.

J. Management of Vulnerability

The respondents were thoroughly informed as to how the study will be conducted and were given the opportunity to ask questions and seek for clarifications. For respondents below 18, parental consent was attached to the Informed Consent Form. This sought the permission of the parents to allow their child to be involved in the study with the assurance that their involvement with the researchers will cease after the administration of questionnaires and conduct of interview. Also, with the permission of parents, respondents above and below 18 were given the freedom to choose voluntarily to whether or not participate in the research.

K. Risk/Benefit of Ratio

In compliance with the ethical protocols of research production, the participation of the respondents in the study posed no harm as the provision of Informed Consent Form, Parental Consent of respondents below 18, and the respondents' voluntary participation in the study. The researchers discussed among the respondents that the latter will be benefitted from the study as this will allow them to identify their level of public speaking

anxiety, which according to previous literatures may hamper effective oral productions, if not addressed properly. The researchers also explained that the creation of a support mechanism geared towards the optimization of oral communication skills among students through the reduction of speech anxiety will help these learners in their public speaking endeavors in Grade 12 and beyond. Moreover, the respondents' identity, PRPSA scores, and responses to interview questions were treated with utmost confidentiality. Also, the researchers discontinued the administration of the questionnaires and the conduct of interviews if these caused discomfort and inconvenience among the participants. Finally, the researchers explained that the respondents will contribute to the final output of the study which is the crafting and implementation of a speech anxiety reduction mechanism, hence, deemed beneficial not only to them and to Saint Mary's University, but also to the schools they represent.

L. Assent Consent

The respondents were provided information about the conduct of the study and were given opportunity to ask questions and clarifications, along with the Informed Consent Form and Parental Consent.

M. Terms of Reference

The study is owned by Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya vis-à-vis Project WEALTH. As part of the dissemination plan, the extended abstract will be published in SMU website.

Results and Discussion

The study generally aims to examine the factors that affect the level of public speaking anxiety among Senior High School students. This section presents the results and discussion anchored on the specific problems forwarded.

Table 3. *Level of Speech Anxiety of Senior High School Respondents*

	Frequenc y	Percen t	Mea n	S D	QD
Very low level of anxiety	50	11.4	4	1	Very high level of anxiety
Moderately low level of anxiety	24	5.5			

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Moderate level of anxiety	126	28.6
Moderately high level of anxiety	82	18.6
Very high level of anxiety	158	35.9
Total	440	100.0

The study examined the level of public speaking anxiety among Senior High School students. Findings revealed that a significant proportion of students experienced high levels of anxiety. Specifically, 35.9% of the respondents reported a very high level of anxiety, followed by 28.6% who indicated a moderate level, and 18.6% who experienced a moderately high level. In contrast, only 11.4% of students reported a very low level of anxiety, while 5.5% had a moderately low level. The overall mean anxiety level was 4.00 (SD = 1.00), which corresponds to a “moderately high level of anxiety.” These results suggest that majority of Senior High School students face considerable anxiety when engaging in public speaking activities, indicating the importance of implementing strategies and interventions to help them manage their anxiety and enhance their communication skills, and public speaking performance. According to Richmond and McCroskey’ (1998), people with this level of public speaking anxiety tend to have a range of very high anxiety. Moreover, in most, if not all, public speaking situations, they are likely to go to considerable lengths to avoid these speech activities. It is unlikely they can become successful public speakers unless they overcome or significantly reduce their anxiety.

To further validate the findings, the researchers conducted an online interview about what the respondents felt before, during and after the performance. Most of the respondents answered, “Nakakahiya po akong magsalita sa harap. Sobra yung kaba ko.” (I feel embarrassed speaking in front. I feel extremely nervous), “Natatakot po akong mapahiya” (I fear getting embarrassed), “Di ko po alam minsan pano sasabihin yung thoughts ko” (I do not know how to express my thoughts), “Nabablangko po ako sa harap” (I suffer from mental block when in front of the class). Some answered that they felt very nervous during the speech and embarrassed after the speech. Others said that delivering a speech in English is a challenging task, due to lack of vocabulary and fear of being laughed at due to grammatical lapses. Upon evaluating the responses, it can be said that the common factors that contributed to the respondents’ high level of anxiety were nervousness, embarrassment, and fear of judgment, and lack of vocabulary skills. Research indicates that the fear of making mistakes often stems from a fear of negative evaluation and the possibility of embarrassment. This can significantly hinder language learners’ willingness to engage in speaking activities (Kang, 2020).

Also, Kitano (2001), emphasized in his study the effect of fear of negative evaluation on students’ English learning anxiety. Moreover, the studies conducted by Putri (2014), and

Ong and Zambas (2021) revealed that senior high school students experienced moderately high and very high anxiety during their speech performance. Likewise, the study of Haloc (2016) revealed that the college sophomores have very high level of anxiety during their impromptu speech performance. In an earlier study, Liu (2006) conducted a survey on English class anxiety on students taking English listening and speaking class in universities of China. The result shows that most of the students felt anxious during their speaking class as they felt a high level of anxiety in responding to their teacher's question or when they were about to speak or present a speech in class speak alone.

Hence, high levels of anxiety, if not managed well may hamper the production of optimum results in oral communication activities. This coincides with Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis which posits that anxiety interferes with learning a second language and speaking achievement.

Table 4. *Difference in Level of Speech Anxiety of Students when Grouped According to Profile Variables*

Profile	Groups	f (n=440)	Mean	SD	t-/F-value	p-value
Sex	Male	160	3.36	1.27	-3.230***	0.001
	Female	280	3.78	1.33		
Type of School	Public	308	3.54	1.36	-2.037*	0.042
	Private	132	3.82	1.21		
Strand	TVL	146	3.79 ^A	1.20	3.655*	0.013
	STEM	120	3.64 ^A	1.38		
	HUMSS	88	3.70 ^A	1.22		
	ABM	86	3.22 ^B	1.47		
First Language	Ilocano	119	3.71	1.26	0.621 ^{ns}	0.602
	Filipino	278	3.56	1.37		
	English	18	3.67	1.41		
	Cordilleran language/s	25	3.84	0.94		

*ns- not significant, *** significant at $\alpha=0.001$, *significant at $\alpha=0.05$, Mean groups who do not share a common letter are significantly different from each other.*

The study sought to determine whether there were significant differences in students' public speaking anxiety when grouped according to sex, type of school, strand, and first language. An independent samples *t*-test revealed a statistically significant difference between male ($M = 3.36$, $SD = 1.27$) and female students ($M = 3.78$, $SD = 1.33$), $t(438) = -3.230$, $p = .001$, with female students reporting higher levels of anxiety. The results corroborate with that of Linter & Belovecova (2025) who found that women are more prone to public speaking anxiety. This may be due to stereotypes confronting females that tend to question their competence and assertiveness. This may cause pressure among women,

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hence, leading to heightened level of public speaking anxiety. Moreover, another key factor is fear of negative evaluation. Females are generally more concerned with how they are perceived, especially in evaluative situations (Linter and Belocova, 2025). This concern can intensify speech anxiety, particularly in academic or professional settings where performance is publicly judged. On the contrary, the studies of Alamri and Qasem (2024), Plandano, et al. (2023), and Haloc (2016) revealed no significant difference in the participants' level of anxiety when grouped according to profile, which means that anxiety level remains the same regardless of sex.

Another independent samples *t*-test showed a significant difference based on the type of school, with students from private schools ($M = 3.82$, $SD = 1.21$) experiencing higher anxiety compared to those from public schools ($M = 3.54$, $SD = 1.36$), $t(438) = -2.037$, $p = .042$. Though this needs further investigation, higher level of public speaking anxiety among students of private schools may be attributed to the more academic stress than their counterparts in government schools. This academic stress may be evident in the conduct and evaluation of public speaking activities and outputs.

Moreover, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to examine differences in public speaking anxiety across strands, and the results were statistically significant, $F(3, 436) = 3.655$, $p = .013$. Post hoc comparison using mean groupings indicated that students in the ABM strand ($M = 3.22$, $SD = 1.47$) had significantly lower anxiety compared to those in TVL ($M = 3.79$, $SD = 1.20$), STEM ($M = 3.64$, $SD = 1.38$), and HUMSS ($M = 3.70$, $SD = 1.22$). Overall, the students experience moderately high to high levels of anxiety. This means that regardless of the strand, anyone can be subjected to a high level of anxiety towards public speaking. This means that even if the student is enrolled in a strand that focuses on speech activities such as HUMSS, the student can still experience high level of speaking anxiety. Furthermore, the studies of Putri (2014), and Ong and Zambas (2021) corroborate with the results. On one hand, Putri (2014) found that Grade 12 students from a private school in Indonesia experienced high level of anxiety in delivering speeches. On the other hand, Ong and Zambas (2021) found that regardless of strand, students in a private school in Mindanao experienced moderately high to high levels of anxiety. The moderately high level of anxiety across the varied strands poses several implications as regards managing oral communication classes. Since people within this category tend to avoid public speaking and may find most public speaking situations as problematic, possible interventions may be made such as the adoption of current strategies in managing speech anxiety.

Another one-way ANOVA was performed for first language, but the result was not statistically significant, $F(3, 436) = 0.621$, $p = .602$, indicating that students' first language did not significantly affect their level of public speaking anxiety. These findings suggest that sex,

school type, and strand are associated with differences in anxiety, while first language is not. This goes contrary to the researchers' initial assumption that students whose first language is English have low levels of public speaking anxiety.

Table 5. *Relationship Between Students' Level of Public Speaking Anxiety and Exposure to English Reading Materials*

Level of public speaking anxiety	Pearson Correlation	Exposure to English reading materials
	p-value	.174***
	n	.0001
		440
<i>Pearson r</i>	<i>Qualitative Description</i>	
<i>±0.80 – ±0.99</i>	<i>Very High Correlation</i>	
<i>±0.60 – ±0.79</i>	<i>High Correlation</i>	
<i>±0.40 – ±0.59</i>	<i>Moderate Correlation</i>	
<i>±0.20 – ±0.39</i>	<i>Low Correlation</i>	
<i>±0.01 – ±0.19</i>	<i>Very Low Correlation</i>	
*** significant at $\alpha=0.001$		

To determine whether there is a significant relationship between students' level of public speaking anxiety and their exposure to English reading materials, a Pearson product-moment correlation was conducted. Results revealed a statistically significant but very low positive correlation between the two variables, $r = .174$, $p < .001$. This suggests that as students' exposure to English reading materials increases, their level of public speaking anxiety tends to slightly increase as well, although the relationship is weak. Despite being statistically significant, the strength of the association is minimal, indicating that exposure to English reading materials has a limited relationship with public speaking anxiety among the students. Though the strength of association is minimal, exposure to English reading materials such as novels, newspapers, academic texts, and online articles may help in minimizing public speaking anxiety.

Based on the interviews conducted, lack of vocabulary, difficulty of structuring thoughts, and fear of judgments are primary concerns. This result suggests that regular reading not only enhances language competence that regular reading not only enhances language competence, but also improves confidence in verbal expression. Hence, exposure to English vocabulary, sentence structures and rhetorical styles may help students feel more prepared and articulate, reducing the anxiety related to public speaking. This is supported by the study of Querol, James, Haloc, Paulino and Gatan (2015), establishing the relationship between confidence and oral proficiency.

Also, reading improves language processing, awareness of syntactic forms and idea organization. These skills are transferrable to speaking. According to Krashen's Input

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Hypothesis (1885), comprehensible input through effective reading leads to natural language acquisition. Hence, when students are well-read, they are more likely to participate meaningfully with other communicators because they have contextual knowledge and language skills to share insights in public speaking activities.

Guided by the results which yielded a very high level of public speaking anxiety among the senior high school respondents, the researchers would like to propose a support mechanism to help students reduce their public speaking anxiety. The support mechanism is grounded on the theoretical foundations framing the study and with the principles of lowering the students' Affective Filter, implementation of cognitive reframing, strength-centered assessment and skills training. The mechanism will be conducted for 5 weeks, 1 session per week and one and half hours to 2 hours will be allotted per session.

Furthermore, the mechanism may be implemented by teachers of oral communication subject among senior high school students. The researchers expect that after implementation of the support mechanism, there will be a considerable decrease in the level of public speaking anxiety among senior high school students. The activities encompassed within the given scheme may be conducted during oral communication classes or may be an extension activity during the students' free time. This support mechanism is titled, "Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism". The program is anchored on the following objectives: 1) reduce anxiety related to public speaking, 2) build confidence and peer support, 3) encourage regular practice in safe and non-evaluative spaces and 4) confidently develop public speaking skills. Figure 3 includes the steps in the proposed support mechanism.

Figure 3
Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism

<p>Week 1: Understanding Fear</p> <p>Activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Administration of Richmond and McCroskey's Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (1998) 2. Sharing of personal experiences with public speaking 3. Conduct of workshop on understanding anxiety, symptoms and causes
--

Week 2: Managing Anxiety

Activities:

1. Conduct of breathing exercises and confidence-boosting activities
2. Conduct of workshops on positive visualization and cognitive reframing
3. Crafting of personalized anxiety coping plan

Week 3: Basics of Public Speaking

Activities:

1. Interactive discussion on voice projection and conduct of nonverbal communication games
2. Presentation of speechwriting and speech delivery guidelines
3. Delivery of 1-minute speeches
4. Constructive feedbacking and encouragement circles

Week 4: Harnessing Linguistic Skills

Activities:

1. Interactive discussion on significance of getting exposed to English reading and/or viewing materials
2. Organize reading, viewing and group discussion sessions
3. Presentation of individual and collaborative public speaking activities
4. Constructive feedbacking and encouragement circles

Week 5: Showcasing Speech Prowess and Reflections

Activities:

1. Presentation of speech variety show in front of class or volunteer audience
2. Constructive feedbacking and encouragement circles
3. Reflection activity on "My Growth as a Public Speaker"
4. Administration of Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA)

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following conclusions can be derived:

1. There are 440 respondents who agreed to participate in the study. Significant proportion of senior high school students experience high levels of anxiety which may hamper the effective delivery of public speaking presentations.

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2. Female respondents experience higher levels of anxiety than males, while respondents coming from private schools experience higher anxiety compared to those from public schools. Moreover, students in the ABM strand had significantly lower anxiety compared to those in TVL, STEM and HUMMS. Also, sex, school type, and strand are associated with differences in anxiety, while first language is not
3. Though the relationship is statistically weak, there is a significant relationship between students' level of public speaking anxiety and their exposure to English reading materials which include books, newspapers, and internet articles among others.
4. With most of the respondents experiencing high levels of anxiety, it is highly suggested that a support mechanism to address public speaking anxiety be crafted. The support mechanism allows for support of activities related to the reduction of public speaking anxiety in less rigid learning environment and constant monitoring of speaker's performance.

From the preceding conclusions, the following are recommended:

1. Since the respondents' level of anxiety fall from moderate anxiety to moderately high level of anxiety, increase in anxiety levels related to public speaking among students may be prevented by encouraging students to share their anxiety with their trusted teachers or friends, or to seek advice and help on how to overcome their speech anxiety. Equally valuable would be the administration of the PRPSA survey at the onset of the oral communication subject and before the term ends.
2. The level of public speaking anxiety of the respondents differs significantly according to their sex, school type and strand, therefore equal opportunities for exposure to public speaking activities, and instruction for effective speech delivery be provided across variables.
3. Since a significant relationship between public speaking anxiety and exposure to English reading materials was established, it is recommended that reading, listening to and viewing of English learning resources be maximized among students.
4. The proposed support mechanism, "Speak Easy: A Public Speaking Anxiety Reduction Support Mechanism" is highly recommended for review and eventual implementation to help the curriculum developers, school, administrators, teachers, and learners, relative to oral communication.
5. Based on the study, future researchers are recommended to include other factors like age, personality traits, and scores in public speaking activities that might impact the level of speech anxiety among students.

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Appendices

Appendix A. Informed Consent Form

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We, faculty researchers from Saint Mary's University, sincerely invite you to participate in a study titled FROM FEAR TO FLUENCY (EMPOWERING VOICES): A PUBLIC SPEAKING ANXIETY REDUCTION AMONG STUDENTS VIA SUPPORT MECHANISM. The study will be conducted from August 2024- December 2024. You are given the time to contemplate whether or not you would like to participate. Also, please do not hesitate to ask questions for clarifications. The purpose of this study is to determine the level of public speaking anxiety and its possible relationship to sex, strand, first language and exposure to English reading materials. Furthermore, it aims to craft a mechanism to reduce public speaking anxiety among senior high school students.

You are one of the selected respondents. Please be informed that your participation is voluntary, and you can withdraw at any time without explanation. Should you choose to participate in the study, you shall be answering a questionnaire containing the following: the general demographic profile, the PRPSA that aims to measure the level of your speech anxiety. You may also be chosen for an interview regarding your experiences in public speaking, and possible ways upon which to address public speaking anxiety. We, the researchers, will also request for the impromptu speech scores from your oral communication teachers, but your names will be withheld for privacy purposes. It is estimated that your participation in the study will only take not more than 30 minutes. There is no known risk in your participation in the study, however, you will be contributing to the existing knowledge on public speaking, and the results of this study will benefit the academe, and the community.

If you are willing to participate in the study and is below 18, we are to provide you with a parental consent to be signed by your parents or guardians. May we request that the parental consent be given back to us after two days?

You shall not receive any payment for your participation nor any reimbursements. Even if you have chosen to participate voluntarily, you have the right to refuse to continue and any information you have already provided will not be used in the study. Rest assured that your privacy is our utmost concern, and all your answers will be treated with strict confidentiality. The accomplished questionnaires will be retrieved only by the researchers and your identity will be anonymized. The data you provided will be transferred to excel in number-coded format. Except for the researchers, no one will be able to identify you as the respondent in this study. After the study is completed, collected data will be carefully discarded.

The results of this study may be disseminated within Saint Mary's University vis-à-vis Project WEALTH of SMU Research Center. Also, the study may be submitted for publication in national or international journals. For any matter concerning this study, you can contact Mrs. Lysel I. Haloc through the following mobile number: 09159437537 or Mrs. Maria Ines R. Minia: 09278883411 or via email: lhaloc@smu.edu.ph and miminia@smu.edu.ph

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This study is approved by the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary's University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph.

Appendix B. Certificate of Consent

I voluntarily agree to participate in this study. I understand that I can withdraw from the study, without repercussions, at any time, whether before it starts or while I am part of the survey or interview, in which case the material will be deleted.

My participation is subject to the following conditions:

- That adequate safeguarding will be provided to maintain the privacy and confidentiality of my responses.
- That my name will not be used to ultimately identify my responses instead, code numbers will be used
- The investigation has been described to me by the researcher, who has answered all my questions

Print Name of Participant: _____

Signature of Participant: _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]: _____

Appendix C. Parental Consent

With the provided information, we the researchers humbly ask for your permission as their parents/guardian to allow your child/ward to be part of our study titled FROM FEAR TO FLUENCY (EMPOWERING VOICES): A PUBLIC SPEAKING ANXIETY REDUCTION AMONG STUDENTS VIA SUPPORT MECHANISM as our respondents.

The participation of your child is voluntary, s/he can or cannot participate in the study according to her/his willingness with your permission. Rest assured that their privacy will be prioritized, no information will be disclosed in public.

Thank you and God bless! Respectfully yours,

Lysel I. Haloc
 Maria Ines R. Minia
 Chirbet C. Ayunon

Name of Parent/Guardian _____

Signature of Parent/ Guardian _____

Date: [MM/DD/YYYY]: _____

Appendix D. Questionnaire

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TITLE OF STUDY: FROM FEAR TO FLUENCY (EMPOWERING VOICES): A PUBLIC SPEAKING ANXIETY REDUCTION AMONG STUDENTS VIA SUPPORT MECHANISM

I. Demographic Profile

Name: _____ Sex: _____ M _____ F

Strand: _____

First Language: _____ Date: _____

Exposure to English reading materials : Always Often Sometimes Rarely

II. Personal Report of Public Speaking Anxiety (PRPSA)

Directions. This instrument is composed of thirty-four statements concerning feelings about communication with other people. Indicate the degree to which the statements apply to you. Indicate the degree to which the statements apply to you (1) strongly agree, (2) agree, (3) undecided, (3) disagree, (4) strongly disagree. Work quickly. Record your first impression.

- ___ 1. While preparing for giving a speech, I feel tense and nervous.
- ___ 2. I feel tense when I see the words "speech" and "public speech" on a course outline when studying.
- ___ 3. My thoughts become confused and jumbled when I am giving a speech.
- ___ 4. Right after giving a speech I feel that I have had a pleasant experience.
- ___ 5. I get anxious when I think about a speech coming up.
- ___ 6. I have no fear of giving a speech.
- ___ 7. Although I am nervous just before starting a speech, I soon settle down after starting and feel calm and comfortable.
- ___ 8. I look forward to giving a speech.
- ___ 9. When the instructor announces a speaking assignment in class, I can feel myself getting tense.
- ___ 10. My hands tremble when I am giving a speech.
- ___ 11. I feel relaxed while giving a speech.
- ___ 12. I enjoy preparing for a speech.
- ___ 13. I am in constant fear of forgetting what I prepared to say.
- ___ 14. I get anxious if someone asks me something about my topic that I don't know.
- ___ 15. I face the prospect of giving a speech with confidence.
- ___ 16. I feel that I am in complete possession of myself while giving a speech.
- ___ 17. My mind is clear when giving a speech.

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- ___18. I do not dread giving a speech.
___19. I perspire just before starting a speech.
___20. My heart beats very fast just as I start a speech.
___21. I experience considerable anxiety while sitting in the room just before my speech starts. ___22. Certain parts of my body feel very tense and rigid while giving a speech.
___23. Realizing that only a little time remains in a speech makes me very tense and anxious. ___24. While giving a speech, I know I can control my feelings of tension and stress.
___25. I breathe faster just before starting a speech.
___26. I feel comfortable and relaxed in the hour or so just before giving a speech.
___27. I do poorer on speeches because I am anxious.
___28. I feel anxious when the teacher announces the date of a speaking assignment.

Scoring: To determine your score on the PRPSA, complete the following steps:

Step 1. Add scores for items 1, 2, 3, 5, 9, 10, 13, 14, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, and 34

Step 2. Add the scores for items 4, 6, 7, 8, 11, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18, 24, and 26

Step 3. Complete the following formula:

$$\text{PRPSA} = 72 - \text{Total from Step 2} + \text{Total from Step 1}$$

Your score should be between 34 and 170. If your score is below 34 or above 170, you have made a mistake in computing the score.

Appendix E. Interview Guide

It was found that your level of speech anxiety is _____. Please answer the following questions.

1. Of all the speech activities you have in class, which are you most nervous of? Why?
2. How about the least anxiety-arousing? Why?
3. What speech activity do you enjoy the most?

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4. What boosts your confidence in speaking?
5. How about those that make you nervous? Why?
6. What are the things that you do to improve your confidence in speaking?
7. How can your teachers help you improve your public speaking skills?

